

HISTORICAL REFORMS IN THE FORMATION OF AN ENVIRONMENT OF RELIGIOUS TOLERANCE IN NEW UZBEKISTAN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8273009>

Abstract. *This article talks about the central role of the problem of tolerance in the scientific research of the system of historical reforms, democratic values and customs in the formation of an environment of religious tolerance in New Uzbekistan.*

Keywords: *tolerance, UN, religion, resolution, conceptualization.*

Uzbekistan ratified the UN Universal Declaration of Human Rights at the very first stage of the historic moments of independence. Article 18 of the Declaration states that "Everyone has the right to freedom of thought, conscience and religion" [1]. Another historical document states in Article 18 of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, "This right includes freedom to adopt and practice one's own religion, also includes the freedom to pray together with others, in public or in private, to perform religious and other customs and rituals" [2].

In the main international legal documents of the UN, the development of human rights and freedoms for everyone, regardless of race, gender, language, nationality, religion or health status, ensuring human dignity and respect, and in this way, intolerance is prohibited. tasks and obligations to fight against the manifestations are described. International legal documents on human rights call on every member of the world community to strive with tolerance for the determination of human rights, freedoms and legitimate interests, democracy and the celebration of rights.

As stated in the "Declaration of Principles of Tolerance" published by UNESCO on November 16, 1995, "Exercising tolerance is consistent with respect for human rights, it includes a tolerant attitude towards social injustice, does not mean giving up one's faith or giving in to the faith of others. It means that everyone is free to practice their faith, and everyone should recognize that others have this right as well" [3].

These international legal models were first adopted on December 8, 1992, and were implemented in the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which was adopted in a new version on the basis of the general vote of our people - referendum on April 30, 2023, and national laws developed on the basis of it in the following years. This is another unique confirmation that Uzbekistan is implementing its international obligations with consistency and determination. From the first years of independence, Uzbekistan declared itself a secular state and strengthened it through the Constitution.

At the heart of the concept of secularism is the principle of separating religious organizations from political organizations and not taking religiosity as a basis for everyone. At the same time, the state undertakes to guarantee the rights of religious people. According to Article 12 of our Basic Law, "Social life in the Republic of Uzbekistan develops on the basis of diversity of political institutions, ideologies and opinions. No ideology can be established as a state ideology" [4], the idea of creating an environment of tolerance based on pluralism in our society is reflected.

On the basis of this constitutional norm, the Law "On Freedom of Conscience and Religious Organizations" [5] was adopted in our country.

"Strategy of Actions on Five Priority Areas of Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021" developed at the initiative of the Head of State and approved on February 7, 2017, and "New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026", which is considered its integral continuation within the framework of the development strategy" effective reforms are being consistently implemented in all spheres of our country's life, including ensuring freedom of religion and belief. These can be categorized as follows:

First of all, the effectiveness of the work aimed at creating the necessary conditions for the religious to visit the holy places has increased.

Secondly, a number of facilities have been created for Christians and Jews living in the territory of our country to visit holy places for them.

Thirdly, the number of members of the Council on Religious Affairs of the Committee on Religious Affairs under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan was increased from 9 to 17, and included representatives of all confessions registered in our country.

Fourthly, in order to reduce the impact of extremist ideas in the society, various preventive measures are being carried out in cooperation with state and non-state organizations. About 40,000 events were organized in 2018 alone, and more than 2.5 million people were involved.

Fifth, over the next five to six years, more than 20,000 citizens who were monitored for having connections with religious extremist groups were removed from "special accounts".

Sixth, in 2017, Imam Termizi and Imam Bukhari International Research Centers, Center of Islamic Civilization and International Islamic Academy of Uzbekistan were established in the country.

Seventh, according to the proposals made by the head of state at the conference on "Ensuring social stability, preserving the purity of our holy religion - the need of the times" held in Tashkent on June 15, 2017, the regions should develop the sciences of kalam, hadith, fiqh, aqeedah and mysticism. 5 scientific schools specialized in learning were opened. These centers of enlightenment now serve to study and promote our rich scientific and historical heritage. In this way, it is planned to prevent the religious radicalization of the population and create an atmosphere of mutual harmony.

Eighth, on April 16, 2018, the decree of the President of Uzbekistan "On measures to fundamentally improve the activities of the religious and educational sphere" was adopted.

Ninthly, on the basis of the Islamic Academy of Uzbekistan and Tashkent Islamic University under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the public foundation "Waqf" was established under the International Islamic Academy of Uzbekistan and the Office of Muslims of Uzbekistan.

Tenth, by the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers on May 31, 2018, the "Regulation on the procedure for state registration, re-registration and liquidation of religious organizations in the Republic of Uzbekistan" was approved.

Eleventh, the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers adopted on January 20, 2014 "On measures to improve the procedure for the implementation of activities in the field of preparation, import and distribution of religious materials" on April 19, 2019 additions have been made.

Twelfth, the official ministries of education of Uzbekistan studied the experience of Norway, Denmark, the Netherlands, Italy, Finland, Greece, Belgium and the USA in the matter of religious

education. Work is underway to prepare printed and video products explaining the state policy issues in the field of guaranteeing freedom of conscience and religion.

On December 12, 2018, the UN General Assembly adopted a special resolution entitled "Enlightenment and religious tolerance" [6]. As a result, the US State Department removed Uzbekistan from the list of countries of "special concern" in the field of religious freedom. This resolution is one of the international initiatives put forward by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on September 12, 2017 from the pulpit of the 72nd session of the United Nations. It is noted that the main purpose of this document is to help ensure everyone's right to education, to eliminate illiteracy and ignorance.

The resolution mentions the promotion of the idea of enlightenment and recognizes the importance of integration, mutual respect, protection of human rights, compromise and mutual understanding in order to strengthen security and peace on our planet. The document supports all international, regional and national initiatives aimed at promoting harmony in religions, cultures and inter-confessional relations and combating discrimination against certain individuals on the basis of religion and belief, as well as all a activation of efforts of member states to protect and promote freedom of thought, conscience, religion or belief.

In this regard, the Conference of Ministers on Ensuring Religious Freedom held on July 24-26, 2018 in Washington, the capital of the United States, is important. This event received the special attention of the American public and mass media. Because, firstly, the prestigious conference on this topic was organized for the first time in the history of the USA, and secondly, almost 600 representatives from more than 80 countries of the world took part in it - ministers of foreign affairs, heads of international organizations, religious leaders and civil society activists.

The delegation of our country, led by the Minister of Foreign Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Abdulaziz Kamilov, took part in the conference organized at the invitation of the US Secretary of State Michael Pompeo. The head of the delegation of the Republic of Uzbekistan told the participants of the conference, President Sh. M. Mirziyoev: "Education and enlightenment are the main factors of the well-being of mankind, they encourage people to be kind, generous, and patient" [7] , spoke in detail about the essence of his call and the importance of his initiatives in this regard.

Historical processes in our country fully meet all criteria of modern democracy. In short, the people of the world today are living in a historical stage of human development where sharp turns are taking place. In the age of globalization, one of the most important principles of establishing peace in the world is religious tolerance. This, in turn, requires each person to study other religions, other faiths and traditions while remaining firm in his faith.

As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoev noted, "Today, when the world is changing rapidly, various new threats and dangers are emerging that undermine the stability and solid development of nations, spirituality and enlightenment, moral education , it is more important than ever to pay attention to the desire of young people to learn and mature" [8]. Drawing a relevant conclusion from this sentence, the civilizational changes taking place at the global and regional level are setting new tasks for our science in the historical period.

Today, youth occupy an important place in the modern historical processes of the society of Uzbekistan, and the state and public associations responsible for the field of youth are becoming more and more active. Modern youth are now involved in many social, political and cultural processes, and they are becoming the leading force of the general development of society. Along

with the full social and cultural integration of the young generation into the society, the strengthening of religious and spiritual values is also important in the historical thinking of this layer. At the same time, rapid penetration of factors such as globalization and westernization is creating a "next generation" with new values and norms of behavior in the society of Uzbekistan.

As it was mentioned above, the process of formation of values of the youth of modern Uzbekistan is very complex and requires mutual integration of the efforts of the components of the society and the state of the youth policy. Youth policy can be fully understood and implemented only within the framework of integrated strategic planning of national development, based on the integration of its main goals, tasks, directions and interactions. For the implementation and effectiveness of youth policy, we must rely on sacred religious factors in the formation of a certain ideological pluralism, spiritual-ethical, historical-philosophical value system. After all, it is religion that is the most effective spiritual basis, with the help of which it is possible to fight against ignorance with enlightenment.

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